

A NOTE ON THE UNRELIABILITY OF THE RESORCINOL PERIODATE TEST FOR HYPONITRITES

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Corbet (*Biochem. J.*, 1940, **34**, 1019) refuting the criticism of Rao *et al* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 599) regarding the reliability of his resorcinol periodate test (Corbet, *Biochem. J.*, 1934, **28**, 1575) for hyponitrite, reasserts without giving any details of the method employed by him that the test is useful for distinguishing between hyponitrite and nitrite. In view of this confused position in literature it has been felt desirable to examine and see the reliability or otherwise of this test.

The test solution of hyponitrite was prepared according to the method suggested in Mellor's "Treatise of Inorganic Chemistry" (1928, VIII, p. 405). Freshly prepared solutions of resorcinol ($M/5$) and sodium periodate (saturated) were employed as reagents.

In a neutral or slightly alkaline medium a light pink colour is given not only by hyponitrite, hydroxylamine, borate and bicarbonate, as pointed by Corbet, but by nitrite and nitrate as well, down to a concentration of ten parts per million. Between p_H ranges 1-3, hydroxylamine, hyponitrite and nitrite give an intense cherry-red colour, the intensity of the colour varying with the concentration. The concentration of nitrite should not, however, be more than 1,000 p.p.m., while at p_H 4 the cherry-red colour is not produced till after 30 minutes, at p_H 5 and 6 this colour is not formed. At p_H 7 and 8 a light pink colour is formed, while in strongly alkaline solutions a yellowish green colour is produced which becomes red on acidification. It has been found that the buffers (Rao *et al*, *loc. cit.*) by themselves do not give any colour with the reagents and the excess of sodium chloride before or after the addition of the reagents has no effect. Hence the buffers employed and excess of sodium chloride present along with the hyponitrite have no effect on the production of the colour. Also varying the concentration of the resorcinol or the order of the addition of the reagents or using a mixture of them, has no effect on the colour formation. Therefore, in view of the similarity in production of colour, the test is unreliable and as such is not useful for distinguishing between hyponitrite and nitrite.

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